

PREPRINT

Fernández-Zamudio, M.A., De Miguel, M.D., Caballero, P. (2005). "Adopting Technological and Structural Changes to Horticultural Production in Spanish Mediterranean Regions." *Outlook on Agriculture*, vol. 34, no. 4, 2005, pp. 249–54, <https://doi.org/10.5367/000000005775454652> .

**ADOPTING TECHNOLOGICAL AND STRUCTURAL CHANGES TO THE
SYSTEM OF HORTICULTURAL PRODUCTION IN THE SPANISH
MEDITERRANEAN REGIONS**

M^a A. Fernández-Zamudio (1)

M^a D. De Miguel (2)

P. Caballero (1)

(1) Researchers.

Departamento de Economía y Sociología Agrarias.

Instituto Valenciano de Investigaciones Agrarias (IVIA).

✉ Apartado Oficial s/n. 46113 Moncada (Valencia). Spain.

Tfn: (+34)-96-3424000. Fax: (+34)-96-3424001.

E-mail: mafernan@ivia.es ; pcaballe@ivia.es

(2) Professor.

Departamento de Economía de la Empresa.

Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena.

✉ Paseo Alfonso XIII, 44. 30203 Cartagena (Murcia). Spain.

Tfn: (+34)-968-325418. Fax: (+34)-968-325793.

E-mail: md.miguel@upct.es

ADOPTING TECHNOLOGICAL AND STRUCTURAL CHANGES TO THE SYSTEM OF HORTICULTURAL PRODUCTION IN THE SPANISH MEDITERRANEAN REGIONS

ABSTRACT

The decision-making process of farmers in the Spanish Mediterranean regions was analysed using the function of Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT). The economic, agronomic and social repercussions resulting from adopting a series of technological and structural improvements were evaluated on farms with citricultural and outdoor horticultural production. The introduction of such measures is necessary to improve competitiveness and favour the sustainability of these farms. The outstanding consequences of these innovations were a more efficient use of irrigation water and an increase in the area of vegetable cultivation when mechanized, which counteracted the overwhelming trend in the area towards citriculture.

KEYWORDS: farm adaptation; decision-making; multi-criteria approach; Mediterranean agrosystems

INTRODUCTION

Horticulture in the Spanish Mediterranean regions is of considerable importance because of the favourable natural conditions and geographical situation. The agricultural sector overall is characterized by high costs and a shortage of certain inputs that have not favoured the expansion of cereal production, extensive cattle raising or the production of raw materials for industry and, in consequence, agrarian activity has been centred around the fruit- and vegetable-growing sector, mainly with produce for the fresh food market.

The main horticultural activity is located along the coastal fringe, with citrus and different vegetable species representing the main crops. Citrus are commonly

identified with the agriculture of this area and represent over 80% of the total area of citrus growing in Spain.

Vegetable species have traditionally been grown outdoors, but greenhouse cultivation is now becoming increasingly common. The area used for greenhouse crops has reached more than 28,400 hectares in the region of Almería alone. But, in spite of the great economic importance represented by intensive horticulture, traditional horticulture also has quality, competitive production.

The new productive context within which world horticulture operates (including conditions imposed by world trade and those derived from the EU action programme, Agenda 2000), brings with it a need for continuous restructuring of agricultural systems so as to facilitate the changes that competitiveness demands and that favour mid- to long-term sustainability.

The present work aims to analyse the technological improvements that can be incorporated into fruit- and vegetable-growing systems in the coastal fringe to increase competitiveness in production. Since both the structural and sociological characteristics of farming and the technology introduced in these areas condition this process, it is necessary to consider it in terms of the wider concept of restructuring the agrarian system.

First, a description is presented of the technological improvements that can be considered for traditional farming along the Mediterranean coast, specifying those that can be incorporated into both citrus and horticultural crop cultivation. Second, the current regional legislation is reviewed. This legislation promotes policies attempting to palliate the negative effects on small farms, which are wide-spread in this area, and prevent, to a great extent, favourable changes in the agricultural system as a whole.

We go on to analyse the decision-making process of farmers in order to determine what are the main issues influencing the planning of activities and the weight they have in the decision-making process. Multi-Attribute Utility Theory

has been used to simulate possible scenarios that could arise following the adoption of supposed improvements. From the analysis, it is possible to identify the economic, social and agronomic repercussions arising from any agricultural restructuring considered.

STRUCTURAL CHANGES IN THE HORTICULTURAL SYSTEM IN THE SPANISH MEDITERRANEAN AREA

A major influence on the agriculture of this region is the movement of labour from agriculture to industry and services. However, this has not led to a restructuring of the lands into more economically viable family units and, consequently, only a small proportion of the farms – those still with an adequate workforce and access to capital – can continue through family inheritance (Aulagnier et al, 2002). To this one must add the drawbacks presented by small properties, all of which have led to legislation for the organization and modernization of agricultural holdings (Generalitat Valenciana, 2002).

The aim of this legislation is to favour the formation of business units that are much larger than the traditional family farm and can, to a certain extent, guarantee the continuity of the farming activity, since they allow levels of mechanization and efficiency that are impossible to attain in the individual units commonly found at present. Independently of these innovations, groups of agricultural enterprises are also being formed through cooperatives and other associations, which may equally lead to improvements in the productive structure.

It has also been observed that, due to the trends in farming incomes, the income obtained from part-time manual work is no longer attractive. Those who remain in farming consequently are likely to be more specialized and more fully employed. The use of contract labour is becoming more commonplace, sometimes to the extent of farms being managed totally by hired personnel.

Contracting out farming tasks is very common in citrus cultivation and is also found, to a lesser extent, in vegetable growing. Traditional horticulture demands more continuous attention and greater dedication than citrus-fruit growing, and this has had greater effects on

the areas devoted to citrus than to vegetable growing. The area dedicated to citrus-fruit cultivation has increased considerably, much of it being the result of the introduction of drip irrigation, which has allowed the irrigation of hillsides and other areas where traditional flood watering was severely limited. Given the important water restrictions that exist throughout the region, this is the most widespread technology used in this type of agriculture, but other improvements are still possible, as explained below.

Forecasting how the horticultural production system will evolve

One of the main limitations that this agricultural system must overcome is the abundance of small properties. The aims of forming associated farming units, which are proposed to overcome this, can be summarized as follows:

- To diminish work time, and therefore the need for family manpower. Rural societies aspire to gaining more free time.
- To allow the farmer to take on a greater managerial role and reduce the manpower requirements. This also favours work continuity.
- To create larger farms and allow more complete mechanization, with ample and upgraded machinery.
- To encourage small producers to adopt innovations without giving up their rights as proprietors.
- To allow optimization of some production factors that require the collaboration of several proprietors, eg reducing water consumption, improving waste management and reducing pesticide application, thereby underscoring environmental issues.
- To improve the harvesting of some vegetable crops by means of picking platforms, which provide greater speed of product packing and freshness, avoiding the need for the transport of waste products to the ware- house.

- In marketing, to develop a stronger trading position attracting a more consistent demand and based increasingly on supply contracts.

So far as citrus and vegetable production are concerned, the most important specific innovations have been related to citrus-fruit production and include the following (which are later reflected in mathematical models):

- Plantations should have a suitable plant spacing, so that path width facilitates machinery mobility.
- Greater use of more powerful tractors is a key factor, enabling the use of air blasters, sprayers and shredders for prunings, and reducing manpower to just the driver.
- Extending the use of drip irrigation, together with the implementation of a complete technological package, which permits the more effective use of management and labour and improves the use of other production factors and final quality.

For vegetable crops the following have been considered:

- Extending the use of drip irrigation and automating both irrigation and fertilizer application.
- Maximizing the amount of mechanization for cultivation, as this greatly influences crop planting and also allows drip irrigation to be extended and plastic sheeting and other devices to be used.
- The value of automated harvesting is also notable, especially for potatoes or onion crops, or, with the help of picking platforms, for harvesting lettuce, cabbage, etc.

METHODOLOGY

It is accepted that farmers take decisions by considering several objectives simultaneously. This is why it is interesting to know the weight that each of these objectives has in the decision-making process and the contribution to possible improvements. Numerous authors have opted to use Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT) to tackle this task.

MAUT was developed from the work of Keeney and Raiffa (1976) and Fishburn (1982), and sets out the mathematical requirements needed to support a function of additive utility. Basically, it hypothesizes that the value, U , generated by n attributes (r), which the decision-maker evaluates for the different alternatives, can be represented through a mathematical function:

$$U = U(r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n)$$

If they are also independent from each other, one can make the following additive breakdown:

$$U \{u_1(r_1), \dots, u_n(r_n)\} = w_1 \cdot u_1(r_1) + \dots + w_n \cdot u_n(r_n)$$

The work of Edwards (1977), Farmer (1987) and Huirne and Hardaker (1998) demonstrated that, even though the strict starting requirements are not completely satisfied, this type of utility function allows an extremely close approximation to the true utility function.

On the other hand, Jiménez et al (2001) conclude that the high level of interaction with the farmer, which is needed to achieve the additive utility function, can be avoided if one knows the current behaviour of farmers, since this involves obtaining a utility function according to the values observed in the real world.

Our work starts with the possible objectives that direct, a priori, the decision making of farmers. The attributes, $j(f_j)$, will be a function of the area that is devoted to each farming activity, X_i .

Next the payment matrix is calculated, optimizing the different objectives outlined successively and subsequently solving the system of the following $n+1$ equations:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_i f_{ji} = f_j$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$$

Where:

n is the number of objectives considered.

w_i is the weights of the different objectives, and therefore unknown.

f_{ji} are the elements of the payment matrix.

f_j the values of the objectives in reality, according to current crop distribution.

If, the previous system of equations has a non negative solution, the w_i will indicate the weights for the different objectives. Nevertheless, this does not often happen, because there is no set of weights that can reproduce the farmer's preferences accurately. To come as close as possible to this solution, the sum of the deviation variables is minimized (n_j and p_j) solving the lineal program:

$$\text{Min} \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{n_j + p_j}{f_j}$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_i f_{ji} + n_j - p_j = f_j \quad \text{for } j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$$

According to the publication by Dyer (1977) the previously obtained weights coincide with the following expression of separable utility function, additive and lineal for each attribute:

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{w_i}{k_i} f_i(X_i)$$

where k_i is a normalizing factor, for example the difference between the ideal and anti-ideal values of the different objectives, which can be extracted from the payment matrix.

Some studies in which MAUT has been applied to agricultural realities that are similar to those studied in the present article, are those by Sumpsi et al (1996) and Amador et al (1998), in which certain theoretical aspects of this technique are developed. Gómez-Limón et al (1996) use it as a simulation method to evaluate the consequences of drought in the Andalusia region, and in Gómez-Limón et al (2003), it is used to estimate the risk-aversion coefficients for an irrigated area of northern Spain. Likewise, in the work by Fernández-Zamudio (2003), MAUT is used to evaluate the possible evolution of irrigated agriculture in the Valencia region.

Establishing the mathematical models

The calculations are applied to a farming model comprising a group of different proprietors, as established and promoted by current legislation, and which cover 100 hectares each. The area of Campo del Turia (Valencia) was chosen as a reference area, and here a survey was carried out to collect data regarding representative family farms, which were subsequently validated with agricultural technicians in the zone before the technological criteria were drawn up and introduced into the mathematical models.

Two modelling scenarios have been considered in the calculation. In the first one (Scenario A), the current most common productive context is represented, with little mechanization and less than 40% of the area under drip irrigation. In the second (Scenario B), the general use of drip irrigation is well developed (up to 70% in vegetable and 100% in citrus cultivation), and the possibility of increasing the level of mechanization is considerable.

The decision variables, and therefore unknowns of the established models, are the hectares that should be cultivated in each productive activity. Four varieties of citrus are included (two clementine and two orange varieties) and six vegetable species (in the case of the lettuce, one spring variety and another autumn one). In all cases, both drip and flood irrigation are considered, resulting in 22 decision variables, which are introduced equally in the two scenarios.

The objectives that, a priori, most seem to determine decision making in the Spanish Mediterranean regions are of an economic nature (to obtain maximum profit from the farmed land) and for social reasons, above all to minimize manual labour on the farm and for the owners to have the maximum possible free time. For this reason, the three objectives have been introduced in the following models:

Objective 1: *maximization of the net profit margin of the farm*, expressed mathematically as follows:

$$\text{Max} \sum_{i=1}^n MN_i \cdot X_i$$

where:

MN_i = Net profit margin of the activity i (euros/ha).

X_i = Surface area of the activity i (ha).

Objective 2: *minimization of the total labour used on the farm*, expressed mathematically as:

$$\text{Min} \sum_{i=1}^n mot_i \cdot X_i$$

where:

mot_i = total labour required per activity i and, in hours.

Objective 3: *minimizing the seasonality of labour*, with the aim of achieving a better distribution of manual work. Its mathematical expression coincides with that described by Romero *et al*, (1987):

$$\text{Min} \sum_{t=1}^4 S_t^- + S_t^+$$

Where S_t^- and S_t^+ are, respectively, the negative deviation and positive deviation of the manual labour, with respect to the average for the quarter t .

A series of *restrictions* are introduced into the mathematical models:

- Use of areas equal to the total available.

- Vegetable crop rotation. It is possible to obtain two harvests a year by matching the area devoted to the crop with an autumn–winter cycle to that occupied by a crop with a spring–summer cycle.
- Market limitations, which establish the maximum growing area of clementine, Clemenpons, and by the growing tradition in the area, which fixes a minimum area for artichoke and Navelina orange production.
- Finally, we introduce some specific restrictions derived from the third objective, and according to what was established by Romero et al (1987).

RESULTS

Once the payment matrix has been calculated, optimizing the three objectives successively, the observed real values are very far from the ideal ones, which corroborates the view that farmers base their decisions on considering a variety of objectives at the same time (Table 1).

Likewise, we can see the importance that the different objectives entered in the model have in terms of the decision-making process followed by farmers in this region. Using the observed data, the calculated weights are as follows: 56% correspond to maximizing the net margin (NM), and 44% to minimizing total manual labour (ML). Minimizing labour seasonality was not significant, probably because when considering the reduction of total manual labour requirements, the seasonality of that labour is decreased at the same time.

Given the weight corresponding to the minimum labour objective, ie 44%, it is possible to justify the present choice, in these counties, of farming activities with low labour requirements or that can be managed externally, without using family manual labour.

With the values of importance or weights obtained, and after normalizing the coefficients, the additive utility function was calculated in the following way:

$$U = 5.52 \text{ NM} - 19.37 \text{ ML}$$

Later on, this utility function is maximized in order to obtain crop planning that generates the greatest utility for the farmers under the initial conditions (Scenario A) and also that derived from the simulation of Scenario B (Table 2).

In the cultivation plan obtained from Scenario A, horticultural crops represent only 25%, as opposed to 75% for citrus fruits. But in Scenario B, horticultural crops represent 30%. The importance of these results is based not only on breaking the current trend in a disproportionate increase in citrus-fruit cultivation along the Mediterranean coast, but also on showing that the cultivation of horticultural crops can be viable and occupy 30% of the total available land.

In terms of crop species, one can deduce that, in both irrigation modes, onions respond well to the innovations considered, increasing from 16% in Scenario A to 46.7% in Scenario B. Lettuces grown without mechanization account for 48% of spring crops and all the winter vegetables, while with the improvements they are displaced by cabbages in winter to account for 16.6%.

Potatoes are chosen only for furrow irrigation and when mechanization is adopted, comprising 12.5% of the summer vegetables. Watermelons (18% in Scenario A) rise to 27.5% in Scenario B. Cabbages are not chosen Scenario A, but in Scenario B, they account for 80.7% of the winter crops. Artichokes compete with the other vegetables where manual labour predominates and up to 18% of the area is dedicated to them; however, mechanization reduces this to 13%.

All in all, it would seem that when the crops can be mechanized, the production of watermelon, potato and onion may increase considerably and would seem to be the farming activities to displace citrus growing.

Clemenpons and Navelina varieties of citrus are chosen within the limits imposed by the model, and Lane Late and Clemenules make up around 40% of the total area of citrus grown. In Scenario B, the tendency is for there to be a

slight increase in the area devoted to clementine varieties compared with oranges.

Table 3 presents the results of the net profit margin, labour and irrigation-water consumption obtained through the calculations. In Scenario A, the average net margin per hectare is euros 5,106, while in Scenario B it is euros 5,930, an increase of 16.2%. Labour requirements for the remaining crops are 334 hours per hectare in Scenario A, and 202 hours per hectare in Scenario B, which represents a reduction in labour requirement of 39.6%.

Finally, we have calculated water consumption demanded by each of the two cultivation plans. The average annual water volume per hectare needed in Scenario A is 7,025 m³, while in Scenario B it is 6,808 m³, ie water consumption reduces by 3.1%, a value that should be considered as an environmental improvement to the hydrological conditions in these regions.

CONCLUSIONS

Considering all the results obtained, one can draw the following conclusions regarding the traditional horticultural system in the Spanish Mediterranean region:

- There is a need to introduce a series of technological improvements in order to optimize production factors. These include replacing traditional flood irrigation with drip-irrigation systems, expanding the use of machinery and the power used, as well as integral mechanization, especially for horticultural crops. It is equally necessary to establish collective management units to facilitate the introduction of these technological innovations, since these would have a much greater capacity for these applications than have the current small properties.
- The incorporation and general use of drip-irrigation systems would represent a water saving of over 3%, an important amount considering the natural conditions of the Spanish Mediterranean coast. This saving will be obtained despite the fact that, with the extended horticultural production area, water consumption will increase considerably.

- Movement towards horticultural crops improves the biodiversity of the landscape, combining arboreal species with herbaceous ones, which, together with the successive rotation of horticultural cultivars, can contribute to the survival of beneficial fauna to help with integrated pest control. All these aspects reinforce the sustainability of the agrosystem.
- The technological packages described contribute to decreasing total and specific labour requirements. On introducing a high level of mechanization, the total labour requirement can be reduced by up to 39.6%. There is greater potential economic saving, if one considers that the reduced enthusiasm of the population in these regions to dedicate time to farming activities can be compensated for by increased mechanization.
- The economic objective, the net margin, increases with the technological improvements described. In Scenario B, the increase in the net margin is over 16% compared with the initial situation. This return represents a guarantee of the viability of this production from allowing an acceptable degree of competitiveness

Acknowledgments

We are grateful for the financial aid received from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Technology and the FEDER European Fund (Project AGL 2002-04251-C03-01).

REFERENCES

- Amador, F., Sumpsi, J.M. and Romero, C. (1998) 'A non-interactive methodology to assess the farmers' utility function: An application to large farms in Andalusia, Spain'. *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, Vol 25, pp 95-109.
- Aulagnier, M., Giraud, G., Reggazzi, D., Bertazzoli, A., Caballero, P., Cases, B., De Miguel, M^aD., Calatrava, J., and Cañero, R. (2002) 'Adaptation of fruit and vegetable production systems in Mediterranean Europe: an approach from the study of agricultural farms in four small regions of France, Italy and Spain'. *Outlook on Agriculture*, Vol 31 No 2, pp 79-85.

- Edwards, W. eds. (1977) 'Use of Multiattribute Utility Measurement for Social Decision Making'. D.E. Bell, R.L. Keeney and H. Raiffa (eds.) Decisions. John Wiley & Sons, Chichester.
- Farmer, P.C. (1987) 'Testing the Robustness of Multiattribute Utility Theory in an Applied Setting'. Decision Sciences, Vol 18, pp 178-193.
- Fernández-Zamudio, M^a A. (2003) 'Viabilidad y competitividad en los sistemas hortofrutícolas mediterráneos según su grado de intensificación'. Thesis, Universidad Politécnica de Valencia, 353 p.
- Fishburn, P.C. eds. (1982) 'The Foundations of Expected Utility'. Reidel Publishing Company. Dordrecht, Holland.
- Generalitat Valenciana (2002) 'Ley de Ordenación Territorial del Suelo Agrario y Modernización de las Estructuras Agrarias de la Comunidad Valenciana'. (DOGV num. 4.266, date 7 Juny 2002)
- Gómez-Limón, J.A., Sánchez, F.J., Rodríguez, A. and Lara, P. (1996) 'Evaluación del impacto socioeconómico de la sequía en los regadíos de la Campiña Baja (Córdoba). Una aproximación multicriterio'. Revista Española de Economía Agraria, Vol 178, pp 163-193.
- Huirne, R.B.M. and Hardaker, J.B. (1998) 'A multi-attribute model to optimise sow replacement decisions'. European Review of Agricultural Economics, Vol 25, pp 488-205.
- Jiménez, J.F., Berbel, J. and Torrico, M. (2001) 'Análisis de la toma de decisiones de los agricultores ante cambios en el precio del agua. Modelo de decisión multicriterio.' Revista de Estudios Agro-Sociales y Pesqueros, Vol 190, pp 65-99.
- Keeney, R.L. and Raiffa, H. eds. (1976) 'Decisions with Multiple Objectives: Preferences and Value Trade Offs'. John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- Romero, C., Amador, F. and Barco, A. (1987) 'Multiple Objectives in Agricultural Planning: A Compromise Programming Application'. American Journal of Agricultural Economics, Vol 69 (1) pp 78-86.
- Sumpsi, J.M., Amador, F. and Romero, C. (1996) 'On farmer's objectives: A multi-criteria approach'. European Journal of Operational Reseach, Vol 96, 64-71.

TABLES

Table 1.- Matrix of pay (for scenario-A and 100 hectares)

	Max. Net margin <i>(euros)</i>	Min. Manual labour <i>(hours)</i>	Min. Seasonality <i>(hours)</i>	Reality
Max. Net margin <i>(euros)</i>	646230	439220	439125	459625
Min. Manual labour <i>(hours)</i>	38035	19410	19388	29833
Min. Seasonality <i>(hours)</i>	41978	7350	7350	9775

**Table 2: Distribution activities cultivated according to the modelling scenarios
(Results for 100 hectares)**

DESCRIPTION OF ACTIVITIES:			scenario-A		scenario-B	
			(ha)	% [1]	(ha)	% [1]
VEGETABLES CROPS						
SPECIES	IRRIGATION	CYCLE [2]				
Onion	Furrow irrigation	spring-summer	4	16	3	10
Onion	Drip irrigation	spring-summer			11	36,7
Lettuce	Furrow irrigation	spring-summer	12	48		
Lettuce	Drip irrigation	spring-summer				
Potato	Furrow irrigation	spring-summer			3,8	12,5
Potato	Drip irrigation	spring-summer				
Water melon	Furrow irrigation	spring-summer	4,5	18		
Water melon	Drip irrigation	spring-summer			8,3	27,5
Cabbage	Furrow irrigation	autumn-winter			7,8	26
Cabbage	Drip irrigation	autumn-winter			13,2	44
Lettuce	Furrow irrigation	autumn-winter	20,5	82		
Lettuce	Drip irrigation	autumn-winter			5	16,7
Artichoke	Furrow irrigation	annual	4,5	18		
Artichoke	Drip irrigation	annual			4	13,3 [3]
TOTAL VEGETABLES CROPS:			25	100	30	100
CITRUS CULTIVATION						
SPECIES	VARIETY	IRRIGATION				
Clementine	Clemenpons	Flood irrigation				
Clementine	Clemenpons	Drip irrigation	11,3	15 [3]	10,5	15 [3]
Clementine	Clemenules	Flood irrigation	30	40		
Clementine	Clemenules	Drip irrigation			28,8	41,1
Orange	Navelina	Flood irrigation	3,75	5 [3]		
Orange	Navelina	Drip irrigation			3,5	5 [3]
Orange	Lane-Late	Flood irrigation	1,25	1,7		
Orange	Lane-Late	Drip irrigation	28,7	38,3	27,2	38,9
TOTAL CITRUS CULTIVATION:			75	100	70	100

[1] % with reference to the total hectares of vegetables or citrus

[2] The surface area of the spring-summer varieties is equal to that of the autumn-winter varieties

[3] The % reached coincides with the one limited in the model

**Table 3.- Results for the two modelling scenarios
(for 100 hectares)**

	scenario-A	scenario-B
Net Margin (euros)	510586	593045
Manual Labour (hours)	33403	20191
Consumption irrigation water (m ³)	702460	680808